

Kinetics and Mechanism of Anation of Hydroxopentaaquo Chromium(III) Ion by DL-Phenylalanine in Aqueous Solution

B. K. NIOGY and G. S. DE*

Department of Chemistry, University of Burdwan, Burdwan-713 104

Manuscript received 13 December 1982, revised 4 October 1983, accepted 27 February 1984

The kinetics of substitution of aquo ligands from hydroxopentaaquo chromium(III) ion by DL-phenylalanine in aqueous medium has been studied spectrophotometrically. The following rate law involving the formation of ion-pair has been established in the pH range 3.5 to 5.4.

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k \cdot K_E [\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{OH}]^{2+}_{\text{total}} [\text{PheH}]}{1 + K_E [\text{PheH}]}$$

where K_E is the ion pair equilibrium constant and k the rate constant for conversion of outersphere complex to innersphere complex. The reaction rate is higher compared to water exchange and some other substitution reactions of hydroxopentaaquo chromium(III) ion. Activation parameters have been evaluated. A lower ΔH^\ddagger value for the anation process suggests that both bond breaking and bond making are important in the transition state.

THE kinetics of anation reactions in hexaaquo chromium(III) ion and in hydroxopentaaquo chromium(III) ion by different ligands have been studied¹⁻⁹. In spite of the large amount of work done on chromium(III) complexes, controversy regarding mechanism persists. Furthermore, the aquo ligand substitution in aquocomplexes of chromium(III) by amino acids, except glycine⁸, has not been studied so far. We, therefore, planned to study the kinetics of substitution of aquo ligands in $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{OH}]^{2+}$ by amino acids e.g. alanine, phenylalanine, aspartic acid, β -alanine, proline, etc., and in continuation of our previous studies¹⁰ we report here a study on the kinetics of anation of hydroxopentaaquo chromium(III) ion by phenylalanine in aqueous medium.

Experimental

A.R. quality chemicals were used throughout. $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6](\text{ClO}_4)_3$ was prepared following the method of Moor and Basolo¹¹. Solution of $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{OH}]^{2+}$ (complex I) was prepared *in situ* from $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6](\text{ClO}_4)_3$ by carefully adjusting the pH at 5.0. pK_a of $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$ being 3.8¹², a solution of this at pH 5.0 with λ_{max} 430 (log ϵ 1.45) and 590 nm (log ϵ 1.36) represents the complex I (Fig. 1). Spectra of $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{OH}]^{2+}$ solution at pH 2.8 (Fig. 1; curve III) is given for comparison.

DL-Phenylalanine with pK_1 1.83 ($-\text{COOH}$) and pK_2 9.13 ($-\text{NH}_3^+$), present in Zwitterionic form at pH 5.0 (P_1 isoelectric point¹³ 5.48), was mixed in different molar ratios with $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{OH}]^{2+}$ to give

a maroon coloured solution, which on concentration and keeping over conc. H_2SO_4 gave a product with 1:2 (metal: ligand) composition (complex II). This composition of the (1:2) complex formed in the reaction mixture in solution was confirmed by Jobs method of continuous variation (Fig. 2). The absorption spectra of complex II gave λ_{max} 400 (log ϵ 1.64) and 540 nm (log ϵ 1.7) (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra :
I. $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{OH}]^{2+}$, 0.0025M, pH 5.0.
II. $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{OH}]^{2+}$, 0.0025M; phenylalanine 0.025M; pH 5.0, spectra recorded after 48 h at 50°.
III. $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$, 0.0025M, pH 2.8.

Kinetic measurements were performed in a Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer. Temperature-

equilibrated solution of DL-phenylalanine and complex I of desired concentrations, prepared in solution at pH 5.0, were mixed in reaction vessels

Fig. 2. Jobs plot of Cr(III)-phenylalanine complex. $[Cr(H_2O)_5OH]^{2+} = [PheH], 0.01M$.

and the course of the reaction was followed by measuring the absorbance at 540 nm where a substantial difference exists in the spectra of $[Cr(H_2O)_5OH]^{2+}$ and $[(H_2O)Cr(OH)(Phe)_2]$. Phenylalanine does not absorb at this wave length. The pseudo-first order rate constants for the substitution reaction were obtained by plotting $\log(D_\infty - D_t / D_\infty - D_0)$ against time, where D_∞ , D_0 and D_t are the optical density values at infinite time, in the beginning and after time t , respectively. The pseudo-first order plots were linear (Fig. 3). The rate constants calculated on the basis of least square method were found to be reproducible within $\pm 3\%$.

Fig. 3. Graphical presentation of k_{obs} at 35° . $[Cr(H_2O)_5OH]^{2+}, 0.0025M$; $[PheH], 0.0125M$ (A); $0.020M$ (B); $0.025M$ (C); $0.03M$ (D) and $0.0375M$ (E).

Results and Discussion

Effect of varying concentration of complex I: Complex I concentration was varied at a fixed concentration of phenylalanine ($0.0375M$), fixed ionic strength ($0.015M$) and pH (5.0). k_{obs} values were found to be 17.29×10^{-5} , 19.89×10^{-5} and $20.16 \times 10^{-5} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ at $[complex I]$ of 0.0025 , 0.004

and $0.005M$, respectively at 35° . The rate of reaction is first order with respect to the $[complex I]$,

$$\frac{d[complex II]}{dt} = k [complex I]$$

Effect of varying pH on rate constant: At fixed $[complex I]$ ($0.0025M$), $[phenylalanine]$ ($0.025M$) and $\mu = 0.0075M$, the pseudo-first order rate constants at 35° (Table 1) were found to increase with increasing pH. To explain the pH dependence of rate constant the following equilibrium¹³ is considered.

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF PSEUDO FIRST ORDER RATE ON pH

$[Cr(H_2O)_5OH]^{2+} = 0.0025M$; $[PheH] = 0.025M$; Temp. = 35° ; $\mu = 0.0075M$

pH of the mixture	$k_{obs} \times 10^6 \text{ sec}^{-1}$
3.5	0.34
3.8	0.97
4.2	1.68
4.5	5.40
4.8	7.14
5.0	14.21
5.2	18.69
5.4	21.96

With the decrease in pH the proportion of reactive hydroxo species decreases which decreases the rate. On the other hand the ligand phenylalanine with two dissociable groups exists in equilibrium as

and

With P_1 the isoelectric point being 5.48 , it can be assumed that within the pH range studied for the substitution reaction the ligand phenylalanine exists in the dipolar-ionic form (HL). The contribution of other forms (H_2L^+ and L^-) is insignificant in the reaction process. Thus the pH dependence of the rate constant is due to the change in the ratio of hydroxo-pentaaquo Cr(III) ion : hexaaquo Cr(III) ion.

Effect of varying phenylalanine concentration: The concentration of phenylalanine was varied in the range 0.0125 to $0.0375M$ at a fixed $[complex I]$ ($0.0025M$). The ionic strength and pH also were

kept constant at 0.0075 M and 5.0, respectively. The results given in Table 2, show that the rate increases with increasing [PheH] and at high concentration a limiting rate is reached which indicates a completion of ion-pair formation through the negative end of the ligand zwitterion.

TABLE 2—VARIATION OF PSEUDO FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANT, k_{obs} , ON [PheH] AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURE

[Cr(H ₂ O) ₅ OH] ²⁺ = 0.0025 M; pH = 5.0; μ = 0.0075 M					
[PheH] M	$k_{obs} \times 10^6 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ at				
	30°	35°	40°	45°	50°
0.0125	8.29	9.07	11.71	14.53	18.64
0.020	10.23	12.77	15.70	20.19	26.20
0.025	12.88	14.21	17.10	23.30	30.50
0.030	13.35	15.65	18.80	26.15	34.60
0.0375	14.20	17.29	21.50	29.05	37.60

The following reaction scheme can be proposed to explain the variation of rate due to change in concentration of incoming ligands.

On this basis the rate equation considering the ion pair equilibrium and rate determining step is found as

$$\frac{d[B]}{dt} = \frac{k \cdot K_E [\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{OH}]^{2+}_{\text{total}} [\text{PheH}]}{1 + K_E [\text{PheH}]} \quad \dots (4)$$

$$= k_{obs} [\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{OH}]^{2+}_{\text{total}} \quad \dots (5)$$

where $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{OH}]^{2+}_{\text{total}}$ = total concentration of unreacted substrate

$$\text{and } k_{obs} = \frac{k \cdot K_E [\text{PheH}]}{1 + K_E [\text{PheH}]} \quad \dots (6)$$

where K_E = ion pair equilibrium constant,
 k = rate constant for interchange of outer-sphere complex to inner-sphere complex.

$$\text{and } \frac{1}{k_{obs}} = \frac{1}{k} + \frac{1}{k \cdot K_E [\text{PheH}]} \quad \dots (7)$$

From equation (7) the plot of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[\text{PheH}]$ at constant pH should be linear with an intercept $1/k$ and slope, $1/k \cdot K_E$ (Fig. 4). The values of $k (\times 10^6)$ thus obtained at different temperatures are given in Table 3. The values of interchange rate constant are found to be much greater compared to the rate constant for isotopic water exchange under identical experimental conditions¹⁴⁻¹⁷. K_E values are found to fall within the range 43.0 to 23.0.

Attempts were made to isolate $[(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{Cr}(\text{OH})(\text{Phe})]^+$ but without any success. The complex

$[(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cr}(\text{OH})(\text{Phe})_2]^+$ was always formed under the prevailing reaction conditions. From this observation it is inferred that as soon as one molecule of

Fig. 4. Plot of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[\text{PheH}]$ at various temperature, (A) 30°; (B) 35°; (C) 40°; (D) 45° and (E) 50°.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF INTERCHANGE RATE CONSTANT, k , FOR THE ANATION OF $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{OH}]^{2+}$ BY PHENYLALANINE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURE

Temperature °C	$k \times 10^6 \text{ sec}^{-1}$
30	23.27
35	32.32
40	37.14
45	59.05
50	81.70

phenylalanine enters into the inner coordination sphere, electron density on the metal centre increases due to inductive effect which in turn labilises the remaining water ligands very easily.

Effect of ionic strength on reaction rate: The ionic strength of the reaction mixture was adjusted with sodium perchlorate, considering the net charge on phenylalanine to be zero (isoelectric nature). The pseudo-first order rate constant at 35° was found to be independent of the ionic strength of the mixture studied in the range 0.0075 M to 0.15 M, at a fixed [complex I] 0.0025 M and [PheH] 0.025 M.

Effect of temperature on reaction rate: The effect of temperature on the reaction rate was studied at five different temperatures for different ligand concentration. The values for interchange rate constants (k) as calculated from eq. (7) are given in Table 3.

Activation parameters were also calculated by least square method using Eyring plot of $\log k$ vs $1/T$ (Fig. 5). A much lower ΔH^\ddagger amounting to 12.9 k cal/mol and ΔS^\ddagger -32.5 e.u. were obtained.

TABLE 4—COMPARISON OF ANATION RATE CONSTANT AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS OF ANALOGOUS SYSTEMS

System	Anation rate constant $k \times 10^3 \text{ sec}^{-1}$	Activation parameter		
		ΔH^\ddagger kcal/mol	ΔS^\ddagger e.u.	Ref.
$[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}\text{-OH}_2$	0.41 at 25°	26.20	+0.8	15
$[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{OH}]^{2+}\text{-OH}_2$	< 10.0 at 25°	—	—	17
$[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5]^{2+}\text{-glycine}$	8.8 at 35°	12.8	-10.2	5
$[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5]^{2+}\text{-nitrilotriacetic acid}$	16.6 at „	20.66	-8.8	7
$[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{OH}]^{2+}\text{-alanine}$	39.9 at „	8.14	-48.23	10
$[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{OH}]^{2+}\text{-phenylalanine}$	32.32 at „	12.90	-32.5	This work
$[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5]^{2+}\text{-picolinic acid}$	22.2 at „	22.50	-3.38	9
$[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5]^{2+}\text{-quinolinic acid}$	41.6 at „	24.38	+4.4	19

Fig. 5. Eyring plot of $\log k$ vs $1/T$.

Conclusion: The reaction between $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{-OH}]^{2+}$ and phenylalanine (in zwitter ionic form) involves outersphere association between the two reacting species followed by associative interchange process. Here both the bond breaking and bond making are equally important. This mechanism explains well the rate data and activation parameters of aquoligand substitution by phenylalanine in $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{OH}]^{2+}$. The ligand OH^- present in complex I is labilizing¹⁸ for the replacement of water molecule.

Further, the activated complex formed through outersphere association is stabilized by hydrogen bonding. These assumptions are supported by the faster anation rate by phenylalanine over other substitution process and isotopic water exchange¹⁴⁻¹⁷. Activation parameter, ΔH^\ddagger , of the present system is lower in comparison to other anation reactions of $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{OH}]^{2+}$ except in the case of alanine (Table 4).

Thus the easy rupture of $\text{Cr}(\text{III})\text{-OH}_2$ bond due

to the presence of OH^- with the simultaneous rapid insertion of the outersphere ligand (through hydrogen bonding) into the available innersphere space justifies the high rate of phenylalanine substitution over the water exchange reactions of $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{-OH}]^{2+}$.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. S. K. Siddhanta for encouragement and valuable suggestions and the U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of a Teacher Fellowship to one of them (B. N.).

References

- R. E. HAMM and R. E. DAVIS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 3085.
- R. E. HAMM and R. H. PERKINS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 2083.
- M. KIMURA and J. SHIRAI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1978, 40, 1085.
- D. BANERJEA and C. CHATTERJEE, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1969, 31, 3845.
- D. BANERJEA and S. DUTTACHOUHURY, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1968, 30, 871.
- S. T. D. LO and T. W. SWADDLE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, 14, 1878.
- J. N. MONDAL and G. S. DE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, 19, 25.
- C. POSTMUS and E. L. KING, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, 59, 1208, 1217.
- M. BHATTACHARYA and G. S. DE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, 20, 780.
- B. K. NIJOGY and G. S. DE, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1983, 92A, 153.
- P. MOOR and F. BASOLO, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 1671.
- F. BASOLO and R. G. PEARSON, "Mechanism of Inorganic Reactions", Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1977, p. 32.
- S. W. FOX and J. F. FOSTER, "Protein Chemistry", John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1957, p. 26.
- J. H. ESPENSON, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, 8, 1554.
- R. A. PLANE and H. TAUBE, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1952, 56, 33.
- J. P. HUNT and R. A. PLANE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 5960.
- D. THUSIUS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, 10, 1106.
- F. BASOLO and R. G. PEARSON, "Mechanism of Inorganic Reactions", Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1977, p. 196.
- M. BHATTACHARYA and G. S. DE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, 21, 898.